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An analysis of the potential contribution of the productive sector to economic growth (GDP) and socio-economic welfare: A case study of Zimbabwe (1985-2012).

ABSTRACT: *The research focused on determining the potential economic production capacity and how this can translate into addressing adverse socio-economic issues like unemployment, access to better health care, nutrition, clean water and sanitation, spread of HIV/AIDS and other social amenities. The target population was the key industries contributing 77.4% of the country's GDP namely; Agriculture, Mining, Manufacturing, Transport and communications, Distribution and Tourism, Education, Health, Electricity and water. Multiple regression analysis was used to come up with a model that best explains the time series data. The model results indicate that these industries are operating at an overall average level of 45.5% capacity, meaning that, at full potential, the country can operate at approximately US\$19.9 billion dollars GDP per year. This level of GDP is expected to more than double public expenditure on capital and social welfare projects. It will also increase the households' disposable incomes which will induce demand for key services like health care, education and others. We also expect investment expenditure to increase leading to job creation and improved domestic production which means less dependence on imports and hence more savings at home. However, full operating capacity can only be attained if a consistent policy framework is put in place to attract the necessary investment in small to medium enterprises (SMEs) and labour intensive manufacturing to create more jobs. This is expected to smooth out income distribution within the economy. Investment in infrastructure and tertiary education is critical since this is where innovation comes from. In developing countries, it is increasingly emerging that International business is keen to invest in the extractive industry where the risk is significantly reduced by the short payback period. The economics of this is largely due to corporate governance issues, political instability, inconsistency macroeconomic policies and corruption. This is therefore an area that needs to be addressed to ensure investor confidence*

1.0 Introduction

The study was carried out to evaluate the potential impact of economic growth on the enhancement of the population welfare within the Zimbabwean context given

Developments in other developing economies (in Africa and abroad).

The globally accepted measure of how well an economy is performing is in terms of such statistics as the Gross domestic product (GDP), inflation, interest rate, exchange rate, Balance of payments (BOP) position and so on, (often referred to as "economic fundamentals"). While these numbers are necessary for planning at a national level, in most developing countries they do not seem to be connected or attached to the critical issues pertaining to the socio-economic well-being of the general population in terms of key demographics

like: life expectancy, literacy level, GDP per capita, unemployment, mortality rates (infant and maternal), access to clean water and sanitation, housing, transport, education, agricultural services and infrastructure. Other critical aspects include prevalence of such diseases as cancer, diabetes and HIV and AIDS.

After a decade of long recession, the Zimbabwean case shows that, comparatively, current figures on most of these variables are significantly lower than both regional and global averages. For instance life expectancy for men is 50 and 47 years for women (up from 37 years (2006)), compared to the global average of 62.2 years (World Bank Report, 2011). The improvement from 1996 has largely been due to accessibility of health care, better nutrition, and HIV and AIDS therapy over the past two to three years (the dollarization phase).

Given the background of the study, it can be noted that whilst there is potential capacity in terms of

economic growth, the same cannot necessarily be said for socio-economic welfare of the general population. The objective of this case study is to evaluate the impact of economic growth on population welfare. This is important for us to determine whether the policy framework in place goes beyond economic data that is periodically generated.

It is therefore necessary to evaluate the country's potential economic performance and analyse the possible impact (if any) of this growth on population livelihoods as defined by some of these key demographic variables outlined in section.

1.1 Keywords: *Differencing, Dollarization, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Purchasing Power Parity (PPP), stationary data, and value addition.*

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical literature review

This section focuses on identification and critical analysis of information and literature related to this research project by identifying the theoretical framework, empirical studies carried out on the subject and justification of the current study.

According to Cooper (1998), a literature review uses as its data base reports of primary or original scholarship, and does not report new primary scholarship itself. The author further explains that the primary reports used in literature may be verbal, but in the majority of cases reports are written documents.

Saunders *et al* (2000) says that literature review is carried out to generate and refine one's research ideas, demonstrate awareness of current state of knowledge in one's subject and its limitations. The authors further mentioned that literature review helps to highlight research possibilities that have been overlooked implicitly in research to date, discover explicit recommendations for further research to avoid simply repeating work that has already been done and discover and provide an insight into research strategies and methodologies that may be appropriate to one's research goals and objectives.

In the process of literature review, the key issue for the researcher is to be in a position to synthesise

and integrate the large volume of information that is already available on the subject.

Dependency theorists argue that poor countries have experienced economic growth with little or no development due to the fact that they have functioned mainly as resource providers to industrialised countries over a long period of time. According to analysts, this has largely been a result of dependence on outdated economic models that are based on "accumulation and exportation of raw materials at the expense of value addition".

An opposing argument is based on the proposition that economic growth will lead to development by increasing the average level private income, which means an increase in disposable income which will induce expenditure on human development aspects like education, health, nutrition and so on. According Ranis *et al.* (2000), economic growth and human development is a two way relationship. Concisely, the relationship between human development and economic growth can be explained in three ways. Firstly, an increase in disposable income leads to better access to health care, nutrition, education and other social amenities (*Capability expansion through economic growth*). Secondly, reduced poverty levels lead to improved social outcomes (welfare) (*Capability expansion through poverty reduction*) and finally, social outcomes can significantly improve as a result of better access to health care, education, communication, transport and so on (*Capability expansion through social services*).

John Joseph Puthenkalam's research aims at the process of economic theories that lead to economic development. The existing capitalistic growth-development models need to be modified to incorporate issues that are becoming more and more topical like freedom, Human rights, democracy etc.

Other researchers believe that there is need for some building blocks to be in place for growth and development to occur, key being the need to address property rights issues. This will ensure that the informal sector is included in the mainstream economy with the same opportunities as rest of the players.

According Hanushek and Woessmann (2008), a country's economic development is related to its human development, which encompasses, among

other things, health care and education. These factors are however closely related to economic growth so that development and growth go together.

In the broadest sense, economic development covers key areas like price stability, job creation, sustainable growth and provision of affordable housing, health care and so on.

A number of studies have been done to establish the how economic growth has addressed the

population social welfare; the following have been chosen for consideration.

2.2 Empirical literature review

2.2.1 The case of India.

The case study for India shows that as a result of economic liberalisation in 1991, the country's GDP has been growing in leaps and bounds, averaging 7.4% per year between 2000 and 2011 as illustrated in figure 1 below;

Fig 1: India's GDP growth.

Source: The World bank Group (2010).

This growth has been largely driven by the service industry which has consistently grown faster than the other sectors throughout this period.

This phenomenal growth makes India the tenth largest economy in the world and the third largest in terms of *purchasing power parity* (PPP) adjusted exchange rate. However, on a per capita basis the country ranks 140th in the world.

Unemployment is very high, with a potential labour force of 480 million, 394 million or 86% are employed in the informal sector. Children under the age of 14 years constitute 3.6% of the labour force.

Environmental degradation is another sticking area. Out of the country's 3 119 cities and towns, only eight have got full water treatment facilities, 209 have partial treatment facilities, 144 of them dump

raw sewage in the river Ganges (WHO, 1992). Air pollution levels are much higher than permissible global average 75µg per cubic meter. This has had serious effect on the ecosystem such that exotic species have emerged resulting in disease e.g. the cholera outbreak of 1992.

Prevalence of HIV/AIDS is on the increase with at least 1.6% per 2.8 million people.

2.2.2 The case of Nigeria.

According to the research by Ekpo A. H et al. (2010), post independence economic developments in Nigeria can be divided into four distinct phases:

- (1960-1970) - the pre-oil boom period,
- (1971- 1977) - the oil boom period,
- (1980-1998) - the period of stabilisation and structural adjustment, and
- (1994 – 1998) - the period of guided deregulation.

During the per-oil boom, GDP grew at an average of 3.2% rising to 6.1% during the oil boom period. The 1980's realised negative economic growth due to poor performance in the industry sector (-3.2%) and the manufacturing sector (-2.9%). The Agriculture sector also suffered from depressed commodity prices and the oil-boom which lured labour from the rural sector to urban centres.

Over this period, official statistics indicate that unemployment was estimated at an average of 5%. Based on key social indicators, the economy performed well immediately after independence and during the oil-boom period. However, during the 1980's, the economy was undergoing recession.

2.2.3 The case of South Africa.

According to the World Bank Report (2011), the South African economy is considered the largest in Africa, contributing approximately 24% of the GDP in terms PPP. It is among the four upper-middle class economies in Africa, the other three being Botswana, Gabon and Mauritius. The country's economy is quite diversified, having shifted from primary and secondary to tertiary sector in the mid-twentieth century.

Notwithstanding these developments, South Africa's unemployment rate remains high at over 25% and the poor cannot access the economic opportunities and services available. This has pushed crime levels up. Crime is ranked by 30% of South African businesses as one of major constraints on investment ease of doing business.

South Africa fairs well compared to other emerging economies on affordability and availability of capital, financial markets sophistication, business tax rates and infrastructure. However the country fairs poorly on the cost of labour, educational levels and the use of technology and innovation. This has largely been attributed to political background of the country which was characterised by inequality. Although the country's infrastructure is the best on the continent, it suffers severe bottlenecks, power shortages and needs upgrading.

In April 2011, South Africa officially joined the BRICS group of five emerging economies; Brazil, India, China and South Africa. This is a significant development indeed. However, there is need for concerted effort to address the population welfare issues at home.

2.2.4 The Zimbabwean case.

The Zimbabwean economy has been undergoing a decade-long recession which has resulted in serious distortions of both economic and demographic variables. This situation makes it important for us to take stock of these distortions and evaluate the potentially ideal situation taking into account the economic capabilities of the country's main productive sectors. This involves determination of an appropriate GDP growth model whose impact translates into an aggregate expenditure (AE) model. It is from this information that we can deduce the effect on the demographic variables of interest.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A case study research design was used in this study. This type of research explores a single entity or phenomenon bound by time and activity and also collects detailed information by using a variety of data collection procedures over a sustained period of time. According to G Thomas (2011), case studies analyse "people, events, periods, projects, policies, institutions or other systems that are studied holistically by one or more methods".

3.1 Research population

According to Zikmund (2003) population is any complete group of elements, people, companies, hospitals, stores, or college students that share some common set of characteristics. The research population for this study is comprised of the economy's key productive sectors; that is, the *Primary sector* (Agriculture, hunting and fishing), *Secondary sector* (Mining and Quarrying, Manufacturing and Electricity and water), and the *Tertiary sector* (Transport and communications, Distribution and Tourism, Education and Health). This is studied in connection to population demographics outlined above.

3.2 Data collection procedure.

The study was carried out using primarily secondary data collected from the main economic stakeholders; CZI (Confederation of Zimbabwe industries), Zimbabwe Chamber of Mines, RBZ (Reserve bank of Zimbabwe) and ZIMSTAT (formerly the Central Statistical Office (CSO)).

Personal interviews were also carried out with key personnel to get expert opinion on the quality and reliability of some of the data.

3.3 Data analysis

Analysis of the data was based on the economic theory of National output as measured by the GDP. The GDP measures the total value of goods and services produced in the economy over a given period of time, normally a year.

3.3.1 Theoretical framework

In order to determine the relationship between FDI and economic growth, a theoretical model of the form outlined below will be used based on the following Cobb-Douglas production function as shown below:

$$Y = AK^\alpha L^\beta e^\mu \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where Y is the output, K is capital and L is labour and A is total factor productivity efficiency of production.

3.3.2 Empirical model to be estimated

The time series data in Table 1 below was transformed and regression analysis performed to establish the *GDP growth model* based on the relative contribution of each industry, defined as follows;

$$\log GDP = \log a + \beta_1 \log AGRIC + \beta_2 \log DITO + \beta_3 \log ED + \beta_4 \log ELW + \beta_5 \log FINS + \beta_6 \log H + \beta_7 \log MAN + \beta_8 \log MIN + \beta_9 \log TRAC + \mu$$

Where;

$\log AGRIC$ is the natural logarithm of agricultural sector;

$\log DITO$ is the natural logarithm of annual interest rate;

$\log GDP$ is the natural logarithm of gross domestic product;

$\log ED$ is the natural logarithm of education sector;

$\log ELW$ is the natural logarithm of electricity and water

$\log FINS$ is the natural logarithm of finance and insurance sector

$\log H$ is the natural logarithm of education sector;

$\log MAN$ is the natural logarithm of manufacturing sector;

$\log MIN$ is the natural logarithm of manufacturing sector

$\log TRAC$ is the natural logarithm of transport and communication sector.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$; are parameters to be estimated and they measures the slope of the regression equation and

μ is the error term or the random residual term. It is composed of two components which are errors of sampling and purely disturbance random error (other factors which affect the dependent variable but not included in the model). Inclusion of logarithms also helped to reduce the variability on the minimum and maximum values of the variables.

In order to address issues of validity and reliability, the time series data was tested and transformed (*differenced*) to ensure that it is *stationary*. In time series econometrics, a time series is said to be stationary if its mean, variance and auto covariance (at different time lags) are constant (or the same). If the data is not corrected for stationarity, the estimated model will be incorrect and hence produce spurious results.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND KEY FINDINGS.

4.1 The Population data.

The target population for the study was the key industries in the economic sectors given in section (3.2). Time series data pertaining to the performance of these sectors for the period 1985 to 1999 is given in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Industry performance (US billion dollars) - (1985-1999).

Industry	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999
Agri culture	0.999	0.990	1.127	1.117	1.130	1.111	1.079	0.906	0.912	1.009	0.927	1.117	1.097	0.977	1.091
Mini ng	0.277	0.228	0.331	0.335	0.355	0.352	0.327	0.275	0.288	0.312	0.331	0.312	0.341	0.445	0.222
Man	1.730	1.134	1.141	1.160	1.178	1.101	1.174	1.143	1.144	1.134	1.163	1.166	1.141	1.144	1.117
Elect rwt	0.111	0.138	0.180	0.220	0.232	0.299	0.116	0.113	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111
Finsu re	0.322	0.334	0.338	0.447	0.550	0.545	0.448	0.451	0.554	0.541	0.616	0.544	0.445	0.452	0.522
Distr ibuti on	0.819	0.991	0.996	1.122	1.164	1.134	1.150	1.100	1.106	1.106	1.115	1.134	1.133	1.138	1.100
Educ ation	0.344	0.444	0.448	0.480	0.550	0.548	0.441	0.444	0.444	0.444	0.444	0.515	0.554	0.444	0.444
Healt h	0.909	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111	0.111

Source: ZIMSTAT, *Zimbabwe Compendium of Statistics, 2000*.

4.2 Data analysis.

4.2.1 GDP contribution by Industry.

From the time series data above, the average contribution to GDP by these key industries can be rated as in figure 1 below:

From the figure 1, it can be noted that these industries contribute a combined total of 77.4% contribution to the Gross domestic product.

4.2. 2 The results from ordinary least squares.

Multiple Regression analysis was performed based on the fact that GDP growth is dependent on the performance of the key industries outlined above.

Independent Variable (industry)	Difference	Stationarity Process	ADF Test Statistic	Critical levels			Decision
				1%	5%	10%	
Agriculture	1	Intercept	-4.679878	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Mining	1	Intercept	-4.712277	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Manufacturing	1	Intercept	-5.148489	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Transport	1	Intercept	-3.92949	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Electricity	1	Intercept	-4.124472	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Distribution	1	Intercept	-4.005275	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Education	1	Intercept	-3.945332	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Health	1	Intercept	-5.04354	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary
Finance	1	Intercept	-3.955354	-3.7487	-2.9969	-2.6381	Stationary

Source: Raw data.

After the first differencing, the data was tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic (ADF) and the results are presented in table 2 below;

Table 2: Unit Root test using ADF Test at first difference I (1)

4.2.3 Analysis of the results.

Regression analysis on the transformed data gives the following results;

Dependent Variable: GDP-1
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 01/14/13 Time: 10:18
 Sample: 1980 2005
 Included observations: 26

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.884319	0.067259	13.14789	0.0000
AGRIC-1	0.118042	0.054278	2.174750	0.0450
DITO-1	0.243840	0.102756	2.372986	0.0305
ED-1	0.245002	0.163453	1.498914	0.1534
ELW-1	0.055940	0.050540	1.106846	0.2847
FINS-1	0.146397	0.064892	2.256001	0.0384
H-1	-0.066807	0.051746	-1.291070	0.2150
MAN-1	0.224967	0.097489	2.307607	0.0347
MIN-1	0.094243	0.103209	0.913124	0.3747
TRAC-1	-0.017825	0.059184	-0.301181	0.7672
R-squared	0.995363	Mean dependent var		2.846229
Adjusted R-squared	0.992754	S.D. dependent var		0.061241
S.E. of regression	0.005213	Akaike info criterion		-7.391632
Sum squared resid	0.000435	Schwarz criterion		-6.907748
Log likelihood	106.0912	F-statistic		381.5911
Durbin-Watson stat	2.366805	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000

It can be deduced from the *t-Statistic* results that all coefficients of the independent variables (industries) are significantly different from zero. In other words, GDP growth is explained by performance of these industries. In fact the coefficient of determination (*R-Squared*) suggests that 99.6% of the changes in GDP are explained by changes in these industries. However, it is important to note that the negative coefficients for Health (H-1) and Transport (TRAC-1) can be explained by the serious deterioration in infrastructure that has occurred in these sectors over this period as a result of hyperinflation that was experienced in the economy which hindered capital investment.

The estimated GDP equation, (ii) above, can then be stated as follows;

$$\text{GDP-1} = 0.88 + 0.12 (\text{Agric-1}) + 0.24 (\text{Distribution-1}) + 0.25 (\text{Education-1}) + 0.06 (\text{Electricity-1}) + 0.15 (\text{Finance-1}) - 0.07 (\text{Health-1}) + 0.22 (\text{Manufacturing-1}) - 0.02 (\text{Transport-1}) + 0.09 (\text{Mining-1}).$$

..... (iii).

We use this model to forecast the expected GDP when industry is operating at full capacity. This analysis follows.

4.3 Operating capacity (%) by industry. After a decade long of economic downturn, very little if any investment has been undertaken to capacitate the local industry. Basic infrastructure for the Health and Transport sectors in particular are in a state of disrepair due to lack of scheduled maintenance. As a result, the majority of these industries have been performing at way below their design capacities. The current performance level statistics for various organisations are given in table 3 below:

Table 3 Estimated operating capacity (%) by Industry.

	Current
Industry	Capacity (%)
Agriculture	55.0%
Mining	40.7%
Manufacturing	44.2%
Electricity & Water	30.2%
Finance & Insurance	56.5%
Transport & Communications	35.0%
Distribution & Tourism	58.0%
Education	56.0%
Health	33.7%
Total	45.5%

Sources; CZI, Manufacturing sector Survey, 2012.

Zimbabwe Chamber of Mines.

Ministry of Lands, Agriculture and Extension services.

Using data from figure 1 above, we can estimate the current contribution to GDP by each industry using the current GDP estimate of US9.9 billion dollars (2012). From these estimates, we can deduce the full capacity (100%) contribution of each sector as illustrated in table 3 below:

Table 2 : Potential industry contribution to GDP.

	Current	current capacity GDP	Full capacity GDP
Industry	Capacity (%)	Contribution (\$US Billion)	contribution (\$US Billion)
Agriculture	55.0%	1.46	2.66
Mining	40.7%	0.40	0.98
Manufacturing	44.2%	1.98	4.48
Electricity & Water	30.2%	0.22	0.71
Finance & Insurance	56.5%	0.64	1.13
Transport & Communications	35.0%	0.65	1.85
Distribution & Tourism	58.0%	1.55	2.68
Education	56.0%	0.61	1.08
Health	33.7%	0.16	0.48
Total	45.5%		

Sources; CZI, Manufacturing sector survey, 2012.

Ministry of Lands, Agriculture and Extension services.

From the above data, it can be noted that most of the industries are performing below 50% of full capacity, (with an overall industry average capacity utilisation of 45.5%). We can then apply logarithms and use them to estimate the potential GDP using the GDP function (iii) defined in section 4.2.3 above. This gives:

$$\text{GDP-1} = 0.88 + 0.12(\log 2.66) + 0.24(\log 2.68) + 0.25(\log 1.08) + 0.06(\log 0.71) + 0.15(\log 1.13) - 0.07(\log 0.480) + 0.22(\log 4.48) + 0.09(\log 0.98) - 0.02(\log 1.85) = 1.1872.$$

This means that the GDP, given this potential capacity is equal to ten raised to the power of 1.1872, that is $10^{1.1872}$, which equals US 15.4 billion. Since this represents 77.4% of the GDP, (from Fig 1 above) this implies that the full economic potential is US 19.9 billion per annum.

4.4 Implications on aggregate expenditure.

This level of GDP has got several implications on the expenditure patterns, especially at an aggregated level. On a national level, there are three GDP expenditure categories identified in economic theory namely;

- a) Total consumption,
- b) Gross capital formation and
- c) International trade sector.

Total consumption is the sum of public (Government) consumption and private (household) consumption. On the other hand gross fixed capital formation is made up of public and private sector investment. It also includes changes in inventories held. The international trade sector is concerned with net exports of goods and services.

At the current level of GDP (US 9.9 billion dollars), expenditure by category is given in table 3 below:

Table 3: GDP by expenditure categories (1980-2005).

CATEGORY	% OF GDP	GDP (US 9.9 Billions)	GDP (US 19.9 Billions)
1. Total consumption	88.40	8.75	17.59
a) Public consumption	13.07	1.29	2.60
b) Private consumption	75.33	7.46	14.99
2. Gross capital formation	17.00	1.68	3.38
a) Public investment	16.70	1.65	3.32
b) Private investment	0.30	0.03	0.06
3. International trade sector	(5.40)	(0.53)	(1.07)
a) Exports of goods & services	8.78	0.87	1.75
b) Imports of goods & services	14.18	1.40	2.82

Sources: Zimbabwe Government and IMF estimates, 2012.

5.0 FINDINGS.

The analysis from the previous section shows that the country's industry is operating at an overall average level of 45% capacity, meaning that, with the necessary investment in place, the country can operate at full capacity potential of approximately US19.9 billion dollars GDP per year. This is slightly almost double the current GDP estimate of US9.9 billion dollars. An increase in GDP to this national potential will result in the following possible aggregate expenditure scenarios;

- Public consumption increases from US1.29 to US2.6 billion dollars. This is approximately 101% increase. We expect this to result in more social security and welfare projects, pension payouts and

improved remuneration in the public service.

- Private consumption will increase from US7.46 to US14.99 billion dollars. We expect that with higher disposable incomes, households will direct the bulk of their expenses towards health and education. We also expect this to translate into more demand for other key services like reliable transport and communication infrastructure, access to better accommodation and living conditions, nutrition, security, water and sanitation. As a result, this will have an impact on other demographic variables like life expectancy, infant mortality rate and prevalence of HIV/AIDS. Overall, we would expect a marked improvement in these socio-economic indicators to levels

comparable to regional and global benchmarks.

- Gross capital formation will also increase from US1.65 billion to US3.38 billion dollars. Expenditure on investment both public and private, especially Health and Transport infrastructure, is expected to double. This means job creation, which will go a long way in reducing the level of unemployment, officially pegged at 90% (the highest in the SADC region so far). It also means more production at home, which will reduce dependency on imports thereby enhancing domestic savings.

5.1 CONCLUSION.

In light of the findings discussed above, the country's industry base presents huge potential for economic growth which can lead to significant improvement in the socio-economic welfare of the local population through addressing adverse demographic issues, (which are poorest by regional standards so far), like unemployment, high numbers of economic refugees regionally and abroad, a poor health delivery system, high prevalence of disease especially HIV and AIDs. The majority of the local population can hardly live on US1.00 per day. The transport and communication network infrastructure is in a state disrepair but represents one of the most expensive services by regional standards.

However, full operational capacity of these industries means that concerted efforts must be made to attract the necessary investment through formulation of an enabling and consistent policy framework that is investor friendly enough to raise the necessary capital. It has been noted that generally international investors have been shying away from investing in Africa for reasons of political instability, violence and corruption. As a result, they have tended to concentrate on investing in the extractive industry where they bring their money and do whatever it takes to get their return in terms of gold, diamonds and others, then leave. This form of investment tends to generate growth at an aggregate level without significant job creation.

There is need to concentrate on investing in small to medium enterprises and labour intensive manufacturing to create more jobs. This is expected

to even out income distribution. Investment in infrastructure and tertiary education is critical since this is where innovation comes from.

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